

the partial availability of boiling points in literature, it could, however, be only investigated for NaOH and KOH. The T_b data^{1,8} of the concerned (1663°K and 1593°K respectively) yield a value of $U_o/T_b \approx 0.12$ which may be assumed to be satisfactorily constant for the remaining members of alkali halides. With reference to U_o data^{11,12}, the ratio viz., $U_o/T_b \approx 0.10$ is again on a lower side to discredit these lattice energies. Further, using the relation $U_o/T_b \approx 0.12$, one may estimate the hypothetical boiling points of LiOH, RbOH and CsOH as being 1792°K, 1633°K and 1317°K respectively.

Moreover, the ratio of $U_o/T_m \approx 0.31$ observed in alkali hydroxides is almost twice as compared to the mean value of U_o/T_m for alkali halides⁶ (≈ 0.16). A similar trend of higher U_o/T_m with respect to U_o/T_b is pointed out in case of alkali halides as is maintained in this study as well.

Husain *et al*⁴, have established a constancy of the product of lattice energy (U_o) and equilibrium interionic distance (r_o) for the members of alkali halides. Applying this relation to another family of alkali hydroxides, the average $U_o r_o \approx 500$ K cal mole⁻¹ Å is obtained. $U_o r_o \approx 500$ in conjunction with the sum of ionic radii¹⁵ of Fr⁺ and OH⁻ ions ($r_o = 3.20$ Å) provides the U_o of FrOH to be 156 K cal mole⁻¹. A proper inclusion of this value in Table 1 tends to be a rational estimate along with the U_o ⁸⁻¹⁰ data of its preceding companions. This is what one should demand from the first principles.

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Acetylacetonanthranilic Acid as a Gravimetric Reagent for Zirconium

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SEVERAL organic reagents have been tried¹⁻⁹ for the gravimetric determination of zirconium in its salts, alloys and ores. Very little work has been done with Schiff base complexes of Zr(IV) with anthranilic acid as the basic nucleus. O-mercaptoacetamidobenzoic acid, a derivative of anthranilic acid has been successfully used for the gravimetric estimation of Zr(IV)¹⁰ by Geetha and Padmini. N-acetylacetonanthranilic acid, a tridentate ligand was first prepared by Mehta et al for the estimation of copper¹¹. In the present note authors have described the use of N-acetylacetonanthranilic acid as a dependable reagent for zirconium.

The reagent was prepared by the condensation of acetylaceton and anthranilic acid in the presence of a few drops of piperidine¹¹. The reagent was characterised by its I.R. spectrum and elemental analyses. m.p. 162°. Equivalent weight was found out to be 208.

The reagent was used in the form of a 10% solution in 1:1 aqueous alcohol. 1 ml. of this solution is sufficient for the determination of 50 mg of ZrO₂. Only a slight excess of the reagent should be used since it is not highly soluble in water.

Zirconium can be conveniently determined in the range of 0.05-0.2 g. Zirconyl chloride solution was prepared in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid and standardised using mandelic acid as the precipitating agent⁴.

Procedure :

ZrOCl₂ solution (10 ml) was diluted to 150 ml. After adjusting the pH of the solution between 3.5 and 4.0 using ammonium acetate 10% hot solution (20 ml) of the reagent in 1:1 aqueous ethanol was added with constant stirring. The precipitate was digested for 30 min at 80-90° and cooled. It was filtered after 1 hr through Whatman filter paper No. 42, washed with a hot solution of the reagent, dried and ignited to constant weight in a platinum crucible and weighed as zirconium dioxide. The result obtained (0.1014 g) was in good agreement with the amount estimated with mandelic acid (0.1012 g).

Interference from other ions :

Zirconium was separated from aluminium(III), nickel(II), calcium(II), cerium(IV), uranyl(II), tin(IV), lead(II), germanium(IV), sulphate and nitrate ions when present to the extent of 25% of that of zirconium with an average relative error of

± 0.3%. Serious interference was observed only with iron(III), thorium(IV), titanium(IV), vanadium(V) and lanthanum(III). Similarly fluoride added as a sodium salt also caused interference. Tantalum, niobium and tungsten are not usually present in chloride solution. Other elements have not been investigated but they rarely occur in association with zirconium.

Application to zircon—Well powdered zircon was converted to zirconium oxychloride^{1,2} taking care to remove all interfering ions. A stock solution was then prepared and a suitable aliquot was estimated using N-acetylacetone anthranilic acid. The results thus obtained compared favourably with those given by mandelic acid method.

The analysis of the dark-brown chelate displayed the metal ligand ratio to be 1 : 1.

Found ZrO₂, 34.8 ; C, 41.3 ; H, 4.51 ; N, 4.32%

Calc ZrO₂, 35.99 ; C, 42.08 ; H, 3.79 ; N, 4.09%

The infrared spectra of the zirconium chelate indicated the absence of characteristic absorptions for -OH and -COOH groups. However the strong absorption of the ligand at 1650 cm⁻¹ due to νC=O is shifted to lower frequencies in the chelate and appears at 1600 cm⁻¹. A strong band at 1550 cm⁻¹ due to νC=N is shifted to 1500 cm⁻¹ in the complex. These shifts towards lower frequencies show that C=N and C=O are involved in bond formation. The absence of a band around 1100-800 cm⁻¹ due to ν Zr=O^{1,3-16} rule out the possibility of Zr=O bond in the chelate.

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Bi-ionic Potentials of Uni-bi Anionic System with 'Neosepta' Membranes

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BI-IONIC potentials are complex phenomena and the studies become more complex if the counter-ions are of different valencies due to the unknown parameters like the membrane phase activities and the mobilities of the ions within the membrane. However, several attempts were made by various workers¹⁻³ to study the uni-bi systems for different purposes.

In this short communication the multi-ionic potential equation of Wyllie⁴ is rearranged to a simpler form in case of bi-ionic potential of uni-bi anionic system with two assumptions.

(i) For a high capacity ion-exchanger membrane, the activities of the ions within the membrane may be assumed to be constant over the range of Nernstian response, and

(ii) the intra-membrane mobilities remain constant over the range of permselectivity of the membrane.

The rearranged equation for uni-bi anionic system takes the form as

$$E_{BIP} = -\frac{2.303RT}{2F} \log a_B + \frac{2.303RT}{F} \log a_M + C \dots (1)$$

where C, a constant, is given by

$$C = -\frac{2.303RT}{2F} \log \frac{\bar{a}_M^2}{\bar{a}_B} - \frac{2.303RT}{F} \left[\frac{\bar{a}_B \bar{U}_B - \bar{a}_M \bar{U}_M}{2\bar{a}_B \bar{U}_B - \bar{a}_M \bar{U}_M} \right] \log \frac{2\bar{a}_B \bar{U}_B}{\bar{a}_M \bar{U}_M} \dots (2)$$

$\bar{a}_B$, $\bar{a}_M$ are the membrane phase activities and $\bar{U}_B$, $\bar{U}_M$ are the intra-membrane mobilities of the bivalent (B²⁻) and monovalent (M⁻) anions respectively.